

ISic3360

I.Sicily inscription 3360

Language

Sikel

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Euboia

Place of origin (modern)

Licodia Eubea

Provenance

used as tomb cover, from necropolis of Calvario, 'proprieta Adamo'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 21746

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644865

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 220-222 fig.5

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